

Original Article

Co-Occurrence of Depression Among Adults with ADHD and Cognitive Impairment

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Abstract

The study's main objective is to explore the relationship between adult attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) and cognitive impairment and the possible co-existing depressive symptoms because of these two disorders. A sample of 174 patients diagnosed with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (male, $n = 76$; female, $n = 98$) was selected through purposive sampling techniques from various hospitals and psychiatric clinics in Mansehra and Haripur (KPK) cities. Results revealed that female participants secured higher scores on ADHD than males whereas female patients scored higher on the CFI and depression scale as compared to males. Regression analysis predicted a positive relationship between depression and ADHD, and depression. Regarding gender, the result shows that ADHD, cognitive failures, and depression have a significant intercorrelation with each other among the patients. The regression coefficients for gender ($\beta = 4.587$) and ADHD ($\beta = 0.170$) are statistically significant at $\alpha = 0.05$, except for cognitive impairment ($\beta = -0.033$). ADHD and gender have a positive relationship with depression or predict depression while Cognitive Impairment ($\beta = -.033$) has a negative relation or does not predict depression. The study promotes guidelines to the researchers to investigate various unidentified aspects of ADHD and depression in the context of cognitive impairment.

Keywords: ADHD, Depression, Cognitive Impairment

Introduction

The cognitive aspect of an individual's development is an important factor contributing to healthy adjustment and well-being. Adequate cognitive functioning is an essential element to execute simple activities of daily life, such as bathing, dressing, and more complex tasks, such as managing money, taking medications, etc. Individuals suffering from ADHD can also experience some sort of impaired cognition or mental disabilities that can indirectly lead them toward depressive symptoms.

Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is linked with considerable cognitive, family, social, behavioral, and learning impairment (American Psychiatric Association, Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (2000)). The American Psychiatric Association (APA, 2013) estimates that the ratio of males to females diagnosed with ADHD is approximately three to one (Ramtekkar et al., 2010).

Throughout the life span, attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is extremely co-morbid with a number of psychological problems. The most prevalent disorders are depression, anxiety, and substance-related disorders (Martini, 2022). The National Co-morbidity Survey Replication (NCS-R) by Kessler and colleagues (2010) and Sible et al. (2022) have reported that adults with ADHD symptoms are six times more likely to suffer one or more additional psychological problems in their lives (Shen, 2020). Previous studies have reported that

JOURNAL OF
SOCIAL HORIZONS

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How to Cite:

Perveen, S., Rehman, S., Khan, H., & Shoaib, F. (2024). Co-Occurrence of Depression Among Adults with ADHD and Cognitive Impairment. *Journal of Social Horizons*, 1(2), 1-10.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15320255>

males are more prone to ADHD than females (Albert, 2015) and females show higher depression than males (Sramek et al. 2022).

ADHD and cognitive dysfunction may have a direct effect on each other. Cognitive impairment is commonly reported in clinically diagnosed samples with (ADHD) (Molavi, et al., 2020). Cognitive impairment is defined as a deterioration of mental functioning domains such as short-term memory, attention, assessment and problem-solving abilities, and visual-spatial skills (Harvey, 2022). ADHD and cognitive impairment displayed a strong association with each other as ADHD is thought to be a neurobiological condition involving behavior dysfunctions and cognitive distortions. Commonly memory deficits have been identified as comorbid symptoms in adults with ADHD and specifically, deficits in the verbal working area of memory have been reported (Groves et al., 2020). Depression and cognitive impairment are two interrelated and interdependent concepts, and both can cause and affect each other (Hale et al., 2021). An extensive number of studies have displayed a significant correlation between depressive symptoms and a decline in cognitive functioning, suggesting that depressive symptoms are most common among individuals with cognitive impairment (Zhu et al., 2020).

The co-occurrence of depressive symptoms with cognitive impairment harms resultant physical health, functional status, and mortality (McIntyre et al., 2020). The coincidence of ADHD and depression symptoms is well documented in the studies (Retz et al., 2021). An individual with ADHD may become irritated and depressed because of their symptoms. They may perhaps lack control over the environment and eventually become depressed as they experience repeated failures or conflicting interactional relationships at home, in school, and in other settings. The combined relation of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) and cognitive dysfunction with the co-occurrence of depression among adults is critical and crucial nowadays because these three have an important effect on a person's life. ADHD is a common neurobehavioral disorder that affects about 4.4% of the adult population (Katzman et al., 2017). Overall, numerous research studies are present on the interrelationship of ADHD, cognitive impairment, and depression (Robbins, 2022). The current research study was designed to examine the relationships between ADHD, cognitive impairment, and depression among adults separately and to predict the co-occurrence of depression. It was predicted that gender base differences would exist on all three variables.

Methodology

Sample

The sample of the present study was comprised of diagnosed ADHD patients ($N = 174$; Male = 76, Female =98) who were conveniently selected from the Hospitals and Psychiatry Clinics of (Ayub Medical Complex Abbottabad, DHQ Hospital, Abbottabad, Mansehra, and Haripur).

Instruments

Urdu version of the ADHD Scale

In the present, along with the demographic sheet (including gender and age variables), for screening ADHD, a translated version (Perveen & Shoaib, 2013) of the Adult ADHD self-report Scale (ASRS-v1.1) was used. It comprises 18 items with two subscales reflecting inattention and Hyperactivity/Impulsivity. Each item can be answered on a five-item Likert scale, based on a scale of frequency ranging from "Never" to "Very Often". Overall scores can range from 0-24; that is, scores ranging from 0-16 will not be indicative of ADHD symptoms, while scores greater than 16 will be highly indicative of ADHD symptoms. It has demonstrated good test-retest reliability and validity, and high internal consistency estimates ($\alpha=0.88$).

The Cognitive Failures Index (UV)

For investigating cognitive impairment, the cognitive failures index (Perveen; CFI, 2013) comprises 20 items and two subscales, cognition and executive function, with 5-point response categories (ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree) used. The reliability of the original scales was computed as .84 (Broadbent et al., 1982). The reliability coefficient value for the present sample was computed as .70. Thus, the scale has satisfactory internal consistency to use in the present study.

Zung Depression Scale

The translated version of the Zung Depression Scale (ZDS; Zung, 1965) comprises 20 items that were used to measure depression. It is a self-report instrument with four-point response categories ranging from (A little of the time = 4, most of the time = 1). This measure has a Cronbach's alpha coefficient ranging from .85 (general

populations) to .90 (psychiatric patient sample) across studies.

Procedure

Permission from heads of medical care-providing institutions and other authority persons was sought for the data collection process. Potential research participants were conveniently contacted for the sample selection procedure. In addition to receiving basic information on the study's objectives, prospective participants received assurances that the information they submitted would be kept private. All surveys were given to the study participants after they gave their informed consent and signed a demographic sheet. They were told to answer honestly, leaving no questions marked. The data were gathered between March and May of 2020. Following data collection with the study's goals in mind, 20 SPSS versions were used for data analysis.

Results

The result indicates that there is a noteworthy difference between males and females on the ADHD scale, CFI, and ZDS. Results revealed that as compared to males, female patients show high scores on ADHD, whereas female patients scored higher on CFI and ZDS as compared to males (Table I). The larger value of Cohen's *d* also reveals that females with ADHD are more vulnerable to cognitive impairment and depression.

Table 1

Alpha reliability coefficient of The Adult ADHD Self-Report Scale (ASRS-v1.1), Cognitive Failures Questionnaire (CFQ), and Centre of Epidemiologic Studies Depression Scale (CES-D; N=174)

Scale	Item No.	M	SD	Alpha coefficient (α)
ARSR	18	43.76	10.09	.778
CFQ	25	75.74	16.31	.858
CES-D	20	42.72	7.31	.610

Note: ASRS = Adult ADHD Self-Report Scale; CFQ=Cognitive Failures Questionnaire; CES-D= The Centre Of Epidemiologic Studies Depression Scale.

The result in Table 1 describes the alpha coefficients for ASRS, CFQ and CES-D are 0.778, 0.858, and 0.610, respectively, which indicates that these scales are internally consistent and reliable tools to measure Inattention/hyperactivity, cognition and depression.

Table 2

Mean, Standard Deviation, and t-values of male and female students' scores on ADHDS, CFI, and ZDS (N=174)

Scale	Gender								
	Male (n=76)		Female (n=98)		t(172)	p	Cohen's d	95%CI	
	M	SD	M	SD				LL	UL
ADHD	47.70	7.843	39.82	10.61	3.93	.000	.85	0.24	2.32
CFI	24.75	5.061	27.17	5.36	4.01	.000	.47	1.17	0.28
ZDS	41.06	6.813	44.38	7.47	3.84	.000	0.47	1.47	0.57

$p < .05$

Note: ADHDS = Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder Self-Report Scale; CFI = Cognitive Failures Index; ZDS = Zung Depression Scale.

The result shows that ADHD, cognitive failures, and depression have a significant relationship with each other between males and females. ADHD and cognitive impairment ($r = -.181$) and cognitive impairment and depression ($r = -.137$) showed a negative relationship with each other, while depression and ADHD ($r = .124$) showed positive relationship and were statistically significant at $\alpha = 0.05$.

Table 3

Summary of Intercorrelations, scores on ADHD, CFI, and ZDS (N=174)

Scale	1	2	3
CFI	-	-.181*	-.137*
ADHDS	-	-	.124*
ZDS	-	-	-

* $p < .05$

Note. ADHDS = Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder Self-Report Scale; CFI = Cognitive Failures Index; ZDS = Zung Depression Scale.

Table 3

Summary of linear Regression Analysis: ADHD, Cognitive Impairment, and Demographic Variable (gender) as predictors of Depression($N=174$)

Variables	B	SEB	β	t	p
(Constant	30.939	6.620		4.674	.000
Gender	4.587	1.541	.315	2.977	.004
CFI	-.033	0.045	-.073	-.732	.466
ADHD	.170	0.078	.235	2.186	.031

df = 398; * $p < .05$

Note: ADHD = Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder; CFI =Cognitive Functioning Impairment.

Regression analysis proved the positive relationship between depression and ADHD, and depression and gender. The analysis also proved the negative relationship between depression and cognitive impairment. Regression coefficients of gender ($\beta = 4.587$), and ADHD ($\beta = 0.170$) are statistically significant at $\alpha=0.05$ except for cognitive impairment ($\beta = -.033$). ADHD and gender have a positive relationship with depression or predict depression, while cognitive impairment ($\beta = -.033$) has a negative relationship with or does not predict depression. The study extends further guidelines to the researchers to investigate several unchecked aspects of ADHD and cognitive impairment concerning depression.

Discussion

The main aim of the present study was to explore the interconnection of depression with ADHD and impaired cognition and see gender-based differences in adults. Another objective of the study is to predict the possible co-occurrence of depressive symptoms with both ADHD and cognitive impairment.

The co-relational analysis indicated a negative correlation between ADHD and cognitive impairment ($r = -.181$) and cognitive impairment and depression ($r = -.137$), whereas a positive correlation between ADHD and depression ($r = .124$). Previous findings also yield the same results (e.g., Eyre et al., 2019; Evren et al., 2019) have found a wide variety of cognitive impairments associated with ADHD. The National Comorbidity Survey Replication (NCS-R) by Kessler et al. (2010) found that 30% to 35% of adult patients with ADHD have major depression (Gnanavel et al. 2019).

Exploring the gender-based differences concerning ADHD, cognitive impairment, and depression level, results revealed that the prevalence of ADHD in males was higher than in females (Franceschini, & Fattore, 2021). Such a finding was supported by the previous study by Leache et al. (2021), who estimated that males are two to three times more likely to have ADHD than females. Furthermore, Danielson et al. (2016) reported that females with ADHD had a greater intellectual impairment, but lower rates of hyperactivity and externalizing symptoms compared to males with ADHD (Grskovic & Zentall, 2010; Soluki et al., 2020).

Investigating gender differences regarding depression revealed that females' depression levels were higher than males. Such findings are similar to the findings of Biederman et al. (2006) suggested that ADHD women had higher rates of major depression and cognitive impairment than normal females. The prevalence rate for the co-occurrence of depressive symptoms and cognitive impairment was 4.2% for men and 6.2% for women (Butzbach et al., 2018; Fuhrer et al., 1992).

Investigating and predicting the co-existence of depression among adults by applying the statistical analysis of regression revealed that ADHD and gender scores significantly predicted depression, respectively ($\beta = 4.58, 0.170$) except for cognitive impairment ($\beta = -.033$), which contradicts the existing literature review (Grigoriu-Serbanescu et al., 2020; Lawson et al., 2015; So et al., 2022; Tsai et al., 2019).

Conclusion

The findings of the current study provided information about the relationship between ADHD and cognitive impairment and predicted the co-occurrence of depression with ADHD and cognitive impairment. A strong association was found between ADHD, cognitive impairment, and depression. The present study found gender-based differences with reference to ADHD, cognitive impairment, and depression, indicating males had higher levels of ADHD than females. In contrast, females were more depressive and suffered from cognitive impairment as compared to males. However, the results of the present study concluded that symptoms of depression partially mediated the relationship between ADHD and impaired cognition, while it fully mediated the relationship between ADHD and gender.

Limitations and Suggestions

1. Current study results were based on a self-report questionnaire to assess ADHD, cognitive impairment, and depression, which is liable to subject biases. For future research, it is suggested to use projective techniques for data collection.
2. The study was conducted on a small sample. For future research to achieve the generalizability of the results, it is suggested to conduct a study on a larger sample.
3. Neglecting other demographic variables, only gender base differences were explored on study variables. For Future studies, it is highly suggested to explore other demographic variables i.e., socioeconomic class, family system, age, etc.

Implications of the Current Study

Despite all of the above-mentioned limitations, the current research study has the following significance:

1. Current study results will provide knowledge to researchers and psychologists in the field with the opportunity to better understand the adults' behavioral and cognitive problems more precisely and provide huge information in the field of psychology.
2. Being aware of one's substantial cognitive, family, social, behavioral, and academic impairment, it is also expected that the present study will be helpful in improving the adjustment and well-being of adults in academic, social, and community settings.
3. Current study results are also very helpful in providing a clear understanding about the causal relationship of ADHD and cognitive impairment and the chances of predictive depressive symptoms among adults, as well as the role of behavioral aspects in the development of any individual's personality.
4. The study has implications for clinicians to increase their awareness of the links between ADHD symptoms, cognitive deficits, and predictive depression. It will further help clinicians create treatment plans that include skills and more advanced counseling and therapeutic services, and medications, and to understand how the presence of predictive depressive symptoms affects the relationship between ADHD symptomology and cognitive profiles.

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